
THE ROLE OF THE LINGUO-CULTURAL APPROACH IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation. This article considers hypothetical underpinnings of the linguo-social methodology in showing a foreign language and useful execution of the linguo-social part in showing English in secondary school. Here is given the most consideration to phonetic and social elements in the growing experience and their job in the development of an open demonstration. As of late, a great deal of foreign language courses has shown up in our country, in the commercial of which you can frequently peruse: “You will know the language better than the English sovereign!” Yet a considerable lot of them underline just a mechanical comprehension of the language, without considering the real factors of the nation of the language or other significant elements. For a genuine capacity to peruse and comprehend the text, it is important to consider syntax and jargon, yet in addition a wide range of information on a phonetic and social nature, the real factors of the language, and so on. Different learning methodologies should arise.

Keywords: Linguo-cultural approach in teaching, formation of language activity, development of speech, teaching perception, specific vocabulary, formation of language activity, national political culture.

Introduction. The cutting-edge school defeats the latency of customary strategies for showing a foreign language, zeroed in exclusively on the development of language action. The improvement of discourse concentrates on the language framework and its capability in it. Nonetheless, it is very clear that the phonetic and social components of instructive and strategic modules and, surprisingly, separate courses of a comparative sort can't answer complex issues of concentrating on public generalizations of conduct and insight, types of reasoning, frameworks of significant worth direction, elements of the translation of moral and tasteful qualities, the points

of interest of public political culture, state - overall set of laws. It is important to shape a comprehensive model of a nation that concentrates on instruction as a profile direction of the whole intricate scholarly disciplines about an individual and society. Just inside the system of such a model is it conceivable to have a considerable, substantial investigation of the living space and way of life of the country - the local speaker of the language being contemplated. As of now, the components of semantic and provincial examinations, brought into the course of showing a foreign language, are turning out to be progressively significant. The importance of this work lies in the way that the illustrations of nation concentrate on making understudies need further free colleague with country concentrates on materials. Also, it is semantic what's more, territorial examinations ought to act as a help for keeping up with inspiration, because. incorporates two viewpoints:

- 1) the language is being educated;
- 2) gives data about the country.

The motivation behind this work is to distinguish at the hypothetical level the execution of the phonetic and social part during the time spent learning a foreign language. Colleagues with the way of life of the nation of the language being concentrated on have been one of the principal assignments since the vestige. Showing traditional dialects is beyond the realm of possibilities without social analysis. In the educating of living dialects since the finish of the nineteenth 100 years. In any case, alongside oral discourse, a colleague with the real factors of the nation of the language being considered is advanced.^[1]

This was particularly normal for the German lingua didactic school. In our country, different data about a specific state, showed during the time spent showing a language, is generally called country studies, Germany - social examinations, in American instructive establishments there are courses "language and region"

¹ Arlan M. A. "Linguistic and regional studies in teaching foreign languages in high school." Foreign languages at school №1 - 1990.

(language and region), in the French systemic school there is the idea of “language and civilization” (langue et civilization). In the correspondence of English instructive foundations, the term linguacultural studies are utilized as “linguocultural studies”. In 1992, the Word reference of the English Language and Culture was distributed by Longman. The government state instructive norm among the objectives of showing a foreign language at the fundamental level incorporates teaching schoolchildren an uplifting outlook towards a foreign language, the way of life of individuals who communicate in this language ...

Training through a foreign language includes information on the way of life, history, real factors and customs of the nation of the language being considered, (lingo-social examinations, provincial investigations) the consideration of schoolchildren in the discourse of societies, colleagues with the accomplishments of public societies and the improvement of general culture, consciousness of the job of the local language and culture in the reflection of the way of life of another individual. The primary objective of etymological and territorial examinations is to guarantee open capability in demonstrations of intercultural correspondence, fundamentally through the sufficient impression of the discourse of the conversationalist and unique texts intended for local speakers. Etymological and provincial examinations intend to concentrate on semantic units that most plainly mirror the public attributes of the way of life of individuals - the local speaker of the language and the climate of its presence. The requirement for extraordinary determination and investigation of language units, wherein the creativity of public culture is generally plainly shown, is felt in all cases.

Resolving the issue of concentrating on language and culture simultaneously isn't inadvertent, since this permits you to effectively consolidate components of nation studies with semantic peculiarities, which act for correspondence, yet in addition as a method for acclimating understudies with another reality for them. There are two ways to deal with showing society during the time spent showing a foreign language: sociology and philology. The primary methodology depends on

the discipline generally connected with the investigation of any foreign language. Country studies are perceived as a complex scholastic discipline that incorporates an assortment of data about the nation of the language being examined. Dissimilar to the key sciences on which it is based, country studies incorporate an assortment of fragmentary data. The expression “lingua-social examinations” underscores that this bearing, from one perspective, joins language instructing, then again, it gives specific data about the nation of the language being contemplated. Since the item isn't the nation, however the foundation information on local speakers, in a summed up structure, their way of life would be more right to discuss “social examinations”.^[2]

Be that as it may, the expression “lingua-social examinations” has proactively become solidly settled in the act of showing foreign languages, and maybe it ought to be deserted. In any case, it is important to comprehend the contrast between customary territorial examinations and semantic provincial investigations. If nation studies is a sociology discipline, regardless of what language it is shown in, then etymological and local examinations is a philological discipline, generally educated not independently as a subject, however in language practice classes during the time spent dealing with the semantics of language units. With a philological methodology, it is feasible to set two distinct assignments: 1. Extraction of social data from semantic units. In this situation, culture comes to the front as the fundamental errand of study. This strategy has been predominant for quite a while in the technique of showing Russian as an unfamiliar language. 2. Figuring out how to see or introduce a language unit against the foundation of a picture like that present in the psyche of a local speaker of the language and culture. (We are

² Borisenko M. K. “Some aspects of teaching elements linguistic and regional studies in the senior classes. Foreign languages at school №3 -1997.

discussing a picture framed based on broadly classified affiliations, barring individual, individual ones.)

The picture on which the semantics of a word or phraseological unit is fabricated is made by an understudy of a foreign language successively during the time spent dealing with the importance of a language/discourse unit and shows up completely when the understudy experiences this unit. With this way to deal with chipping away at semantics, on the public social part of importance, not culture, language is brought to the very front of study, and etymological and territorial ability is intended to give open skill, which includes working with comparable pictures in the personalities of the speaker and audience, as it occurs during correspondence. between speakers of a similar language and a similar culture. In this way, the principal objective of etymological and territorial examinations is to guarantee open capability in demonstrations of intercultural correspondence, essentially through the sufficient view of the conversationalist's discourse and unique messages intended for local speakers. Phonetic provincial examinations give an answer for various issues, specifically the super philological issue - a sufficient comprehension of the message, in this manner it goes about as an etymological premise for linguodidactics, yet additionally for interpretation.^[3] All things considered, to decipher, one must as a matter of some importance completely grasp an unfamiliar text with every one of the subtleties of significance, including subtext, references, suggestions, and really at that time, considering the recipient, select the proper reciprocals in the objective language. To investigate the method for language and discourse, organizing them and presenting them in an ideal structure for showing a foreign language is one of the errands of semantics. In this manner, one can unreservedly discuss the phonetic groundworks of the country-explicit viewpoint in showing a foreign language, which

³ Burdina M. I. "Additional material in English for grade 10." Foreign languages at school №1,3,5 - 2002.

ought to be perceived as a feature of the overall etymological underpinnings of its instructing, following up on a standard with different sciences: brain research, instructional method, and so on, as a hypothetical starting point for showing a foreign language overall.

Conclusion. In this way, the lingua-social methodology in showing a foreign language possesses a huge spot. Showing helps for showing present-day English ought to have a useful concentration, the capacity to foster oral and composed relational abilities, in light of the most recent English and American sources, considering the development and improvement of new jargon, the concentrated on discourse behavior, the substance of the illustrations in the English language manuals ought to incorporate every one of the significant minutes that describe life in English-speaking nations. Utilizing extra material on local examinations, and non-standard types of leading illustrations, interest in the subject expands, the program material is better assimilated, and the understudy of the language stays the conveyor of his way of life. In any case, his experience information is enhanced, gained components of the way of life of the nation of the language being contemplated; consequently, he becomes somewhat the conveyor of world culture and starts to more readily comprehend and value his way of life. The educating of culture regarding showing a foreign language plans to move to the understudy at least foundation information that a local speaker has. Such information, fundamentally connected with topography, history, public activity, workmanship and culture, customs, and customs of the nation of the language being contemplated, can be presented as an editorial in Uzbek or English. In this manner, semantic and provincial examinations are solidly remembered for the course of showing foreign languages, as their fundamental component.

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